

Synthesis and Studies of Mesomorphic Properties of a New Homologous Series : n-Butyl *p*-(*p'*-*n'*-Alkoxy)benzoate

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The homologues of the new series n-butyl *p*-(*p'*-*n'*-alkoxy)benzoate exhibit mesomorphism over a wide range of temperatures. The overall series can be regarded as smectogenic as only two members exhibit nematic mesophase. The smectic-isotropic transitions show odd-even effect and the smectic mesophase is a focal conic fan-shaped texture of smectic A variety.

A review of literature reveals that a large number of homologous series with ester linkage exhibit mesomorphic characteristics¹.

Twelve members (methyl to octyl, decyl, dodecyl, tetradecyl and hexadecyl derivatives) of a new homologous series n-butyl *p*-(*p'*-*n'*-alkoxy)benzoate have been synthesised and their mesomorphic properties studied. These compounds are generally synthesised by first reacting the *trans-p*-n-alkoxycinnamic acids² with thionyl chloride and the resultant acid chloride is then reacted with n-butyl *p*-hydroxybenzoate.

Experimental

A typical synthesis of the first homologue, viz. n-butyl *p*-(*p'*-methoxy)benzoate is as follows: *trans-p*-Methoxycinnamic acid (0.01 mol) was refluxed with excess of thionyl chloride on a water-bath for 3–4 h. The excess thionyl chloride was removed by distillation under reduced pressure. The acid chloride was heated on the water-bath with dry n-butyl *p*-hydroxybenzoate (0.01 mol) dissolved in pyridine (8 ml) for 30 min and cooled overnight. The mixture was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The product thus obtained was filtered, washed with dilute sodium hydroxide (0.01N), then with water and recrystallised from ethanol as fine white needles (50%).

The mesomorphic behaviour of the compounds was studied on a Laborlux Leitz 12 polarising microscope fitted with heating arrangement. The compounds were characterised by infrared spectra.

Results and Discussion

The physicochemical properties and transition temperatures of the new compounds are given in

Table 1. The plot of transition temperatures against the number of carbon atoms in alkyl chain is shown in Fig. 1. The first member, viz. the methyl compound does not show mesomorphism whereas the second member exhibits monotropic nematic mesophase only. The third propyl member exhibits monotropic smectic but enantiotropic nematic mesophase though the range of nematic mesophase is very small, and after this all the members show smectic mesophase only. The solid-mesomorphic curve shows a continuous decrease in the transition temperature (Table 1) while the smectic-isotropic curve shows initial rise in transition temperatures which afterwards levels off. This curve also shows the odd-even effect. The range of smectic mesophase is quite wide and is maximum for decyl derivative around 50°.

Extrapolation of smectic-isotropic curve towards methyl member indicates the possibility of monotropic mesophase at about 62° but due to high crystallising tendency of the compound, the mesophase could not be observed. The smectic mesophase as observed under polarising microscope shows a focal conic fan shaped smectic A texture.

The thermal stabilities and other characteristics of the compounds of present series (A) have been compared with other homologous series: (i) isobutyl *p*-(*p'*-n-alkoxy)benzoate³ (B), (ii) n-propyl *p*-(*p'*-*n'*-alkoxy)benzoate⁴ (C) and (iii) ethyl *p*-(*p'*-*n'*-alkoxy)benzoate⁴ (D), where all the four series are represented as RO.C₆H₄.CH=CH.COO.C₆H₄.COOR'; R=n-alkyl group, R'=n-butyl (series A), isobutyl (series B), n-propyl (series C), ethyl (series D).

A comparison of the transition temperatures of these series reveals that increase in alkyl chain length at R' end from ethyl to n-butyl lowers the

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TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES AND TRANSITION TEMPERATURES OF n-BUTYL p-(p'-n'-ALKOXYCINNAMOYLOXY)BENZOATE

R	Transition temp. (°C)			Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
	S	N	I		O	H
Methyl	—	—	79.0	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₅	71.48 (71.18)	6.42 (6.21)
Ethyl	76.0	85.0	92.5	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₅	71.83 (71.73)	6.46 (6.52)
Propyl	74.0	83.0	84.0	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ O ₅	72.26 (72.25)	6.84 (6.80)
Butyl	73.5	—	103.5	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ O ₅	72.70 (72.72)	6.84 (7.07)
Amyl	71.0	—	101.0	C ₂₉ H ₃₀ O ₅	73.18 (73.17)	7.27 (7.31)
Hexyl	65.0	—	106.0	C ₃₁ H ₃₂ O ₅	73.53 (73.58)	7.31 (7.54)
Heptyl	65.5	—	104.0	C ₃₃ H ₃₄ O ₅	73.62 (73.97)	7.41 (7.76)
Octyl	60.0	—	107.0	C ₃₅ H ₃₆ O ₅	74.26 (74.33)	7.90 (7.96)
Decyl	48.5	—	106.5	C ₃₇ H ₃₈ O ₅	74.28 (75.00)	8.71 (8.33)
Dodecyl	50.5	—	106.5	C ₃₉ H ₄₀ O ₅	75.37 (75.59)	8.24 (8.66)
Tetradecyl	61.0	—	106.0	C ₄₁ H ₄₂ O ₅	75.82 (76.11)	8.58 (8.95)
Hexadecyl	59.0	—	107.0	C ₄₃ H ₄₄ O ₅	76.28 (76.59)	9.11 (9.21)

Fig. 1. p-n-Butyl (p'-n'-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoate : (●) solid-mesomorphic, (Δ) smectic-nematic, (○) nematic-isotropic and (⊗) smectic-isotropic.

isotropic transition points to a certain extent. Nematic and smectic mesophase range and thermal stabilities also show a gradual decrease with the increase in alkyl carbon chain length. Another interesting feature is that n- and iso-positions of the butyl group (series A and B, respectively) also affect the mesomorphic characteristics to a good extent. The nematic mesophase which is quite prominent in the compounds having isobutyl group

(series B) is almost eliminated with the n-butyl group (series A). It is perhaps because the overall length of the isobutyl group is shortened as breadth of the molecule is increased enhancing the nematic mesophase range. A comparison of thermal stabilities of the compounds of the present series (A) with those of series (B), (C) and (D) is given in Table 2. It can be observed that with the addition

TABLE 2—THERMAL STABILITIES

	A	B	C	D
Average S-N or S-I transitions	106.5° (C ₉ -C ₁₄)	107.2° (C ₉ -C ₁₄)	115.0° (C ₉ -C ₁₈)	119.0° (C ₉ -C ₁₈)
Average N-I transitions	92.5° (C ₂ -C ₂)	108.7° (C ₃ -C ₆)	115.7° (C ₂ -C ₆)	119.7° (C ₂ -C ₆)
Commencement of smectic mesophase	C ₂ ^a	C ₂	C ₂	C ₂

^aTotal number of carbon atoms in alkyl chain, viz. C₂=ethyl chain derivative.

of one CH₂ unit at R' terminal end from ethyl to n-butyl, the nematic and smectic thermal stabilities show a gradual degradation.

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